

**SMES AND THEIR TRANSFORMATION INTO LARGE
ORGANIZATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF UZBEKISTAN**

Bekimbetova Mariya Maxsetullayevna

MBA graduate of Binary Graduate School

in Tashkent

+998994853242, mariya.bekim@gmail.com

Abstract: SME creation and expansion have been extensively studied in scholarly literature because of their historical significance to the economy. However, there are still several obstacles that limit SME growth prospects today, and these obstacles often differ by country and level of economic development. In order to identify the obstacles preventing SMEs in Uzbekistan from developing into large organizations, this article will examine SMEs in that country. A review of the literature on SMEs, recent governmental reforms, and the effects of these reforms will be done in order to examine the aforementioned issues.

Key words: SMEs, growth and expansion, Uzbekistan, barriers, limitations, reforms, developing countries, post-soviet countries, Former Soviet Union countries

Transition of the world towards digitalization, the boom of popular social media platforms created an immersible change in the way businesses operate and brought lights to the side of small and medium businesses.

Today small businesses have great opportunities to grow and compete equally with large organizations, as if previously SMEs needed to invest on some tangible resources today, they can either substitute it or outsource easily with the aid of the internet. Now they can easily establish their virtual existence and find third parties ready to do for them some of their business functions which will cost much less than if they have spent on materials or did by themselves.

Today Small and medium businesses can no doubt be labeled as the drivers of the economy and their growth. And for countries like Uzbekistan which are at their developing stage, continuity and growth of SMEs is a vital topic for studying so that proper mechanisms will be established to further empower their growth.

The Uzbek market is also facing enormous changes in its economy with its steps towards the transitions of its command economy towards free market economy. It has done enormous work to make this process safe and at the same time fast and today we can see a rising number of small and medium businesses.

Small business in Uzbekistan can be categorized into three groups:

- Sole – proprietors;
- Microfirms with an average annual number of employees employed in manufacturing sectors - no more than 20 people, in the service sector and other non-productive industries - no more than 10 people, in wholesale, retail trade and public catering - no more than 5 people;
- Small enterprises with an average annual number of employees employed in industries: light industry, food industry and building materials industry, provided for by law - no more than 200 people; metalworking and instrument making, woodworking, furniture industry, as well as other industrial and production areas provided for by law - no more than 100 people; engineering, metallurgy, fuel and energy and chemical industries, production and processing of agricultural products, construction and other industrial and production areas provided for by law - no more than 50 people; science, scientific services, transport, communications, services (except insurance companies), trade and public catering and other non-productive areas - no more than 25 people.

Olson (1992) stated that transmission of the economy of former post Soviet Union countries from communism to capitalism is the basis for a new economic system where these small firms have to be put as main actors with an access to those reallocated resources. Respectively, we can state that the starting phase for establishment and

growth of new enterprises in post-Soviet Union countries falls into the time frame when the above “transmission” started to begin.

With the reforms of our second president Mirziyoyev whose actions were primarily concentrated on creating a free liberalized market economy the number of small medium initiatives around the population started to increase at a very high rate.

These ongoing reforms are creating a favorable environment for small and medium initiatives, these actions have the power to alleviate the problems left from the concentrated economy in Soviet times. We can witness positive results upon the rising number of SMEs in our markets, since the Share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the GDP of the country for the year of 2022 counted to be 50.5 (stat.uz, 2022).

During the past decades, a major concern has been the failure of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in transforming themselves into large firms both regionally and globally. We can witness the same situation occurring here in Uzbekistan, despite the government's efforts to increase entrepreneurial activities in our country, we can count only a limited number of truly successful SMEs that were able or have potential to grow into large organizations able to operate both in domestic and international markets.

It is crucial to understand the variables posing obstacles to the growth and sustainability of SMEs as Uzbekistan has just started implementing to create a robust digital economy with the goal of integrating into the global market. Numerous studies have revealed entrepreneurship as one of the main forces behind sustainable development (Hall et al., 2010). The President of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, recently instituted reforms with the goal of improving conditions for SMEs in the country by offering a variety of incentives and developing a supportive infrastructure. With Uzbekistan now placing 69th out of 190 nations in the World Bank's "Doing Business" report, these measures have clearly had an impact.

The globe is gradually but fully digitizing today, opening up enormous chances for businesses to operate across borders and even to benefit from prospects to expand

through partnerships with international companies. In order to join the vast global pie of digital marketplaces, Uzbekistan is likewise interested in creating an open digital market. In this situation, it is essential for local Uzbek enterprises to build strong local SMEs that can expand and run-in step with other foreign businesses in the global market arena in order to safeguard themselves.

More than 62% of individuals working for small businesses in the country in 2018 were functioning as sole proprietorships, according to the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction of the Republic of Uzbekistan; just approximately 16% were registered as small enterprises and micro firms. Looking back at past indications, the slow growth of small businesses during these years may suggest that SMEs struggle with a poor business climate and limited access to capital (Tadjibaeva, D. 2019). On the basis of these assertions, we can observe that a sizable portion of small firms operate under a simplified taxation system, which on the one hand helps business but deters business expansion (due to limits on the number of workers).

It is necessary to identify current obstacles impeding SMEs' ability to expand, whether they take the form of market conditions or erroneous justifications that business owners believe keep them from taking the necessary steps to grow their operations into significant multinational corporations.

In addition to the conventional well-known obstacles facing established businesses, such as a lack of access to financing and ineffective methods for promoting goods and services on domestic and international markets, there are still perceived barriers to entrepreneurship that impede the development of new entrepreneurial ventures. Numerous lines of research have shown that cognitive factors such as low self-confidence, a lack of knowledge and experience, and a strong perception of risk are some of the biggest perceived hurdles to entrepreneurship. This paper aims to contribute to achieving the goals of the above-mentioned Decrees and regulations of our government by identifying the factors that contribute to the discontinuity and interruption of SMEs further growth and also some recommendations will be provided

based on a study of successful cases of international SMEs that grow into large organizations. By identifying the factors that contribute to the discontinuity and interruption of SMEs further growth, this paper aims to bring some contributions in achieving the objectives of the above-mentioned Decrees and regulations of our government by providing some recommendations on the basis of a study of successful cases of SMEs that outgrow into large organizations. This in turn may help aspiring SMEs to lessen those barriers and enhance entrepreneurial ventures in our country by developing successful business strategies for them to grow.

According to earlier research on this topic, Olson, (1992) claimed that the transition of the economies of the former post-Soviet Union countries from communism to capitalism served as the foundation for a new economic system in which these small businesses had to be made the main actors with access to the resources that had been reallocated. In addition, Iakovleva et al, (2014) said that people in post-soviet countries were discouraged from participating in entrepreneurial activity because the government planned and distributed everything on its own.

Uzbekistan and other Central Asian nations who were long-time members of the Soviet Union had a difficult transition to make from their command economy structure to a mixed or free economy. Respectively, we can state that the starting phase for establishment and growth of new enterprises in post-Soviet Union countries coincide with the beginning of the aforementioned "transition." With the beginning of the transition process in these countries many anticipated promotion and boom of entrepreneurial activities but this wasn't the case because there were still some elements left over from the prior condition of the economy.

Significant obstacles including sluggish institutional changes and inefficient resource distribution left over from the Soviet era have not supported the development of productive SMEs (Karymsakov et al., 2018)

The economy of Uzbekistan is typically described as being mixed, meaning that while there is some room for modest levels of freedom, the vast majority of the economy is still controlled by the government. Lack of capital and financial resources

have always been the biggest obstacle for SMEs functionality; however, the state is making efforts to deal with this issue by providing loans, subsidiaries etc. Obviously, the purpose of the government's subsidiary loans and small credits is to promote entrepreneurship. However, since some of the government loans are expressly designed for entrepreneurial activity in certain designated sectors, the question arises as to whether the people have the ability to choose an industry or sector, they choose to operate in.

We have a lot of wonderful instances of foreign SMEs developing into big, well-known companies that do well enough domestically to expand their operations worldwide. Local companies' presence in the international market ensures that both international and local buyers' attitude and perception towards Uzbek goods will rise.

In a number of earlier studies, authors came to the conclusion that the lack of knowledge about export-oriented operations, inadequate infrastructure, corruption, and bureaucracy, as well as low levels of competitiveness, were the main barriers to the growth of SMEs. (McIntyre, 2001; Pasadilla, 2010; Makhmadshoev et al., 2015; United Nations [UN], 2015:35; Sass et al., 2015; Ruziev & Webber, 2017; Gattini & Baiashvili, 2016:19; Vaysman & Podshivalova, 2015) Although there are a large number of studies on SMEs, empirical evidence on the post-Soviet countries is very limited (for instance, see: Akulava, 2015).

Hui-Hong JK Li et al, (2004) during their research carried out on a topic of SMEs business growth: A medium to big effort; tried to find out how some successful SMEs in Eastern countries were able to grow in their size both locally and internationally. Their study's objective was to investigate the business strategies employed by developing MNCs to change medium-sized SMEs. Researchers used an inductive approach to investigate how technology-driven SMEs grow and evolve. With the aim of understanding their key traits, cooperation strategies that improve productivity and update skills and technologies, business models that support organizational and technical learning strategies, and customer base growth, three cases of emerging MNCs companies in the Far East are chosen.

The study's conclusions demonstrate that the observed developing MNCs often took advantage of late-mover advantages in one of two ways.

Some began by comparing themselves to the established global companies and then found ways to get past them, frequently by taking advantage of market niches that MNCs had missed. Other businesses chose a different, riskier approach. They aided OEMs by providing contract manufacturing services, which enabled them to increase their production capacity. The business will then have the chance to grow and become larger. They took advantage of the inflexibility of operations and inefficiencies of existing MNCs by banking on their production capacity to challenge the game's rules. At the time, the authors noted two possible applications for their framework: assisting managers in the field in choosing appropriate growth strategies, and assisting researchers in better comprehending the varied growth models of medium-sized SMEs.

Consequently, based on the review of prior studies on the subject of factors limiting SMEs' growth and case studies on SME-specific transformational techniques that were successful in their further transformation, we may draw the conclusion that, in most situations, the expansion of SMEs is hampered by the terms under which they must operate such as bureaucracy, corruption, inadequate infrastructure as well as the lack of appropriate training available to SMEs to assure their ability to continue operating at the rate of increasing competition. When it comes to the tactics employed by those successful SMEs in Eastern nations that were able to successfully transform into sizable multinational corporations, it is clear that the majority of them were able to expand by putting a strong emphasis on niche strategies in conjunction with technological excellence. Thereby, it's important to keep in mind that the majority of those companies began by mimicking some of the organizational structures of larger companies before creating their own by updating and refining those structures over time.

In light of the above findings, we can suggest local SMEs to continuously watch and learn from large businesses and to put their focus on the market segments that were left or unnoticed by large organizations.

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